

Innovative digital surveillance system for increased safety of Road Restraint Systems (RRS) on highways

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ABSTRACT

The paper describes the design and prototyping of an image-based speed measuring system, which is additionally supported by other sensor technologies (like LiDAR, radar or ultrasound), to obtain information on the two velocity components in the road plane with a simple sensor architecture. This information is essential to characterise the angle of collisions onto and therefore for effective accident reconstruction. The computational load is moved closely to the source of the data (edge computing), thus reducing infrastructure costs, increasing latency and adding an extra layer of privacy by eliminating the need to send video recordings to a remote server.

The potential cost-effectiveness of an edge computing type machine vision architecture would make it possible to sensor long road sections, process the images on the fly and send only the desired result. This computing paradigm aligns with industry requirements for a smart road infrastructure that enables emission reductions and sustainability, and in addition supports the implementation of autonomous mobility and progress towards the goal of zero accidents through Infrastructure-to-Vehicle (I2V) and Infrastructure-to-Everything (I2X) communication (Lozano Domínguez & Mateo Sanguino, 2019).

1. INTRODUCTION

Traditional traffic speed measurement systems (such as induction loops, radars, laser guns, pneumatic tubes, piezoelectric sensors, etc.) are designed to determine the velocity component parallel to the road axis. Only image-based speed measuring systems and LiDAR scanners make it possible to obtain information on the two velocity components in the road plane with simple sensor architecture. This information is essential to characterise the angle of collisions.

Recent advances in Systems-on-a-Chip (SoC) technologies on the hardware side and progress in computer vision models and algorithms on the software side, allow the computational load to be moved closer to the source of the data (edge computing), thus reducing infrastructure costs, increasing latency and adding an extra layer of privacy by eliminating the need to send video recordings to a remote server.

There are 3 major weaknesses to this state-of-the-art, which impact not only highway safety of highways but also their operations. The digital surveillance system for Road Restraint Systems (RRS) devised below seeks addressing such challenges by combining several mature technologies into one holistic system and verify it under representative conditions:

1. Emergency response time between the moment that an accident happens and the arrival of emergency responders (policemen, firefighters, ambulances);
2. Detection of quasi-collisions (situations in which a collision almost happens) and their quantification.

3. Automatic surveillance and predictive maintenance for highway operators.

The European RRS regulatory framework does not include the need of including any smart functionality enabling seamless communication with control centres. For this reason, when an impact against the barrier occurs, there is a period of time where the road operator is not aware of the existence of such impact. Besides, until road workers arrive to the location of the incident, there is no real feedback on the severity of the impact and the damage induced in the barrier, what makes the planning and execution of maintenance operations incredibly difficult to predict and execute. Commonly this increases safety risk and disturbs road users.

It seems there is a niche to explore every aspect connected to the commissioning, installation and operation of a 'smart barrier' concept. Communication protocols between the sensors installed in the barrier prototype and the control centre should be built and tested, with the objective of monitoring data exchange between them. Special emphasis should be put on data security and latency issues in order to guarantee a minimum delay between the occurrence of an accident and the reporting to the control centre.

In sum, a 'smart barrier' should even be able to report on the severity of the accident, as well as on the status of the barrier, hence allowing a more efficient management of road interventions. In addition, the automatic generation of alerts for other road users should be envisioned.

Traditional traffic surveillance systems (to determine the velocity component parallel to the road axis) are mostly deployed in urban contexts today, since their roll-out and maintenance costs are deemed unfit for larger scale deployments on dual or single carriageways. The need to digitise the surveillance for increased security and reduced cost is clear: by not only detecting but also documenting quasi-collisions and various forms of collisions (single vehicle collisions, multiple collisions, etc.), it is possible to apply predictive security planning. With a view to securing black spots (locations which have a higher risk for crashes or collisions than usual), i) infrastructure adaptations, ii) reinforcement of existing road restraint systems (RRS) and iii) automatic emergency response are only some of the improvements that a digital sensor-based system could put forward to significantly improve the performance and cost of RRS.

Developing such a system is therefore quite challenging, as it needs to satisfy several different dimensions and characteristics to become a true asset and a replicable application on the market:

1. **Liability: A high accuracy and adequacy** of a solution is a must to ensure that the collisions or quasi-collisions are detected correctly. A high reliability serves as a valuable evaluation tool of road infrastructures.
2. **Affordability: Low-cost equipment and parts** should be considered to enable high density and replicability for wide road networks and an attractive value for money to road operators.
3. **Non-intrusive: Protection of the privacy of road users** is important for a wide acceptance and can be achieved via a connection to an Artificial Intelligence (AI) back office for real-time analysis of data and predictions via edge computing.
4. **Valid: A multi-dimensional** system, which takes into account three-dimensional variables and covers almost the entire road surface is needed to be able to identify and monitor all road interactions, including not only crashed but also quasi-collisions.

Keeping these guiding principles in mind, a state-of-the-art analysis was launched to identify available solutions and how different technologies could co-operate to form such a holistic system.

2. STATE-OF-THE-ART

A state-of-the-art analysis helps in identifying not only existing gaps in the road surveillance especially of single and multi-carriage highways but also in building on existing technologies by harmonising them to build a new system.

The analysis can be split into 3 different sub-sections:

1. **Existing digitised surveillance for compliance on road infrastructures:** e.g., camera and radar-based speed cameras or video surveillance of intersections.
2. **Existing digitised surveillance for monitoring of road infrastructure conditions:** e.g., analysis and evaluation of infrastructure soundness or AI-advised maintenance protocols.
3. **Existing digital surveillance technologies in other sectors:** e.g., facility security systems with different technologies (BLE, WiFi, GPS, RFID, NFCs, etc.).

2.1. DIGITISED SURVEILLANCE FOR COMPLIANCE

Currently, most digital solutions for the surveillance of the compliance of road users and operators are camera- or image-based (Sun et al., 2006). This includes user-centric systems such as speed traps (which may be camera or radar based) or the surveillance via camera of entire intersections or identified black spots. Another example can be the use of satellite images, which are analysed via an AI-algorithm to ensure that minimum dimensions or geometry of road infrastructure is kept to ensure the safety of road users (e.g., the width of the driving lane, angle of a curve or an appropriate sloping of ascending/descending road infrastructure) (Gupta & Singh, 2014).

All these tools to verify that any road infrastructure is at the base complying with standards or laws collect images or video material, which needs to be obtained, processed, stored and analysed in order to eventually be used as a legal proof. It is therefore required that public authorities - such as national road authorities, transport ministries, police authorities and the alike - commission, monitor and analyse data in a secure way to protect the privacy of persons and companies; these entities cannot share the data publicly or commission third parties to deal with the collected footage.

2.2. DIGITISED SURVEILLANCE OF ROAD CONDITIONS

Another way that digitised surveillance is already in use on European roads is to verify the status and conditions of road infrastructure elements, such as bridges, tunnels or road (horizontal & vertical) marking. In most such cases, road audits are necessary, which are conducted with the help of laser technology, video and photo footage, satellite images or GPS data of trips undertaken on the network (Ahmed et al., 2013).

Such audits, however, do not take into consideration other factors which require more permanent surveillance, such as the detection of black spots. For example, quasi-collisions between vehicles are usually not detected within the regular reporting by police authorities, since they happen spontaneously and often only last split-seconds.

Today most of the surveillance of road conditions primarily focuses on marking and the structural integrity of road infrastructure and not so much on detecting and preventing dangerous spots from a planning perspective.

2.3. DIGITAL SURVEILLANCE TECHNOLOGIES OF OTHER SECTORS

Different digital surveillance technologies from other industries should be reviewed to consider their adaptation to the road infrastructure and road traffic context. Amongst them there are technologies which are already equipped on modern day cars, used in an urban context or in other industries (namely space technologies or software development):

1. **RADAR:** Using Doppler effect to obtain velocity data and Time of Flight (ToF) sensors to measure the distance between emitter and object;
2. **Ultrasounds:** Using ToF sensors;
3. **CAM:** Using the images collected by camera recordings;
4. **ToF CAM:** Using both the images of the camera and a ToF sensor to measure the distance between camera and object;
5. **LiDAR:** Using ToF sensors;
6. **Microwave Detector:** Using the Doppler effect to obtain velocity data;
7. **Light Barriers:** Using a static light beam to detect when objects pass (beam is blocked) and averaging the intensity of the light beam;
8. **Passive/Active Infrared:** Using the radiation of InfraRed (IR) light off objects to detect movement;
9. **Induction Loops:** Using magnetic induction to detect metal objects or identify the presence of vehicles;
10. **Piezoelectric Sensors/Tubes:** Used to steer laser beams or detect pressure (e.g. passing vehicles overhead);
11. **Pneumatic Tubes:** Used to detect pressure of passing vehicles overhead.

The following matrix highlights all technologies' positioning over 13 different variables, which are deemed important for an adequate system design.

Technology	Intrusive	Cost (orders of magnitude)	Transversal velocity accuracy	Parallel velocity accuracy	Range	Field of View	Resolution	Colour	Object classification	3D	Processing cost	Bad weather (fog, snow and rain)	Low light conditions
RADAR	No	100€	Low	High	High	Medium	Low/Medium	No	Low	Yes	Low	Unaffected	Unaffected
Ultrasound	No	10€	Medium	Medium	Low	Medium	Low	No	Low	No	Low	Unaffected	Unaffected
CAM	No	100€	Medium/High	Medium/High	Medium/High	High	High	Yes	High	No	High	Affected	Affected
ToF CAM	No	1000€	High	High	Medium/High	High	High	Yes	High	Yes	Medium/High	Affected	Moderately affected
LiDAR	No	1-10k€	Medium/High	Medium/High	Medium/High	High	Medium	No	Low/Medium	Yes	Medium	Moderately affected	Unaffected
Microwave Detector	No	Expensive	Low	Medium/High	High	Medium	Low/Medium	No	Low	Yes	Low	Unaffected	Unaffected
Light barriers	No	Inexpensive	None	Medium/High	On-place detection average &	None	None	No	None	No	Low	Moderately affected	Unaffected
Passive / Active Infrared	No	Inexpensive	None	Medium/High	On-place detection average &	None	None	No	None	No	Low	Moderately affected	Unaffected
Induction loops	Yes	Expensive	None	Medium/High	On-place detection average &	None	None	No	None	No	Low	Unaffected	Unaffected
Piezoelectric sensors / tubes	Yes	Expensive	None	Medium/High	On-place detection average &	None	None	No	None	No	Low	Unaffected	Unaffected
Pneumatic tubes	Yes	Expensive	None	Medium/High	On-place detection average &	None	None	No	None	No	Low	Unaffected	Unaffected

CONCEPTUALISATION AND SYSTEM DESIGN

Based on the preceding analysis, various sensor configurations may be envisioned for evaluating different blends of radar and ultrasound technologies. These technologies could serve to augment a camera network with the goal of attaining state-of-the-art accuracy in vehicle localization, tracking, and speed determination within a traffic flow. Furthermore, the aim is to address the limitations of cameras, such as poor visibility conditions, in order to enhance overall performance.

Since the location of the sensors affects their performance (e.g. the optimal performance of the cameras is obtained by maximising the height and centring it on the traffic flow and the field of vision increases by approximately 10 metres for every metre of camera height (Klein et al., 2006), different geometries should be tested in order to find a compromise between accuracy and complexity of the infrastructure, taking into account the current legislation in terms of road safety.

From a software perspective, the challenge of attaining state-of-the-art performance with a median absolute error of approximately 1-5 km/h (as reported in Kocur et al., 2018 and Revaud et al., 2021) within the constraints of limited computational resources in edge computing must be addressed. At present, You Only Look Once (YOLO) models are capable of processing medium resolution images at a rate of ~10 frames per second in resource-constrained environments (Feng et al., 2022).

Given that this field is experiencing very rapid progress, the available localisation and tracking algorithms should be evaluated; for their selection, a cost analysis of the SoC hardware solutions with CPU and/or GPU prototyping processors available on the market, as well as an assessment of power consumption, should be undertaken. The software solution selected will set the basic hardware requirements in terms of CPU/GPU, memory, connectivity, and broadband speed, as well as the resolution of the camera and the optical parameters of the objective lenses.

Self-calibration software should be developed to detect the barriers and establish a pixel-to-metre map. From this calibration and the location and tracking information, it is possible to determine the trajectory of the vehicles, including their speed. A software module is developed to combine this information with that of the rest of the sensors (including other neighbouring cameras) to increase the accuracy of the localization and tracking and hence obtain the maximum likelihood estimation of the speed.

To optimize scalability and minimize costs, the architecture of a machine-vision-centered network based on edge computing must be carefully designed. Our team suggests meeting these objectives by deploying a network of sensing nodes (comprised of cameras and SoCs) spaced at intervals greater than ~100m, and gateways spaced at intervals greater than ~1 km to provide Internet connectivity (I2X) through 4G/5G or fiber optic communication and power supply for both node-to-node and node-to-gateway communications.

As highlighted above, the possibility of hybridising the machine vision system with LiDAR, radar or sonar nodes should be explored to complement and cover its weak points.

SYSTEM PROTOTYPING, PILOTING AND FINE-TUNING

A first prototype should be developed and tested in a laboratory setting. In this case, a detailed simulation model should allow both crash tests and near-miss crashes be simulated to verify the accuracy of the system and offer an opportunity to tweak the detection precision.

Prototyping the solution in a lab setting would then help developers gather important insight on the accurate detection of entry angles, velocity and severity of the crash, since all parameters can be monitored closely in this situation, which is not the case in the real-world on an open highway where many error variables and external factors can influence detection.

Once the solution is conceptualised, developed and prototyped, a real-world first pilot deployment should be launched as a restricted Field Operational Test (FOT) on an operational road section. We estimate the pilot should be deployed for at least 3 whole months, during which the team should constantly compare the actual number of reported collisions and quasi-collisions with those detected by the system. By the end of the pilot deployment, a detailed data analysis of available data and the results provided by the system should be compared and quantified to assess the system's accuracy and added value.

The restricted FOT will almost certainly prove necessary to fine-tune the system, e.g. by adjusting camera angles, re-calibrating sensors and/or optimising guidelines for road operators. This fine-tuning exercise would offer the opportunity to quickly improve the system's accuracy and its overall functionality.

CONCLUSIONS

Although digitisation of road barriers and road infrastructure on single and dual carriageways overall is under development in several countries with a view to i) improving detection of single-vehicle collisions, ii) identifying dangerous black spots and iii) increasing the performance of roadside safety systems overall, the system described above looks promising. A prototype is being developed at this point with the aim to deploying it in cooperation with several crash testing houses in order to validate its accuracy and prepare a larger scale pilot on European highways.

The striking points about the system are the low investment and the low effort required to retro-fit existing road restraint systems (RRS), which promises wide market uptake across entire road networks on a national or even European scale. Detecting the frequency of quasi-collisions is of particularly high interest to all relevant stakeholders (drivers on the road, concession operators, manufacturers and authorities), as it would allow detecting dangerous spots and putting in place life-saving and cost-reducing preventive measures (additional RRS, increased roadside maintenance, reduction of travel speed, maintenance of road surface, etc.).

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